

The study titled explores the use of LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) technology to improve the testing of construction aggregates, specifically the Flakiness Index (FI) and Elongation Index (EI). Conducted by researchers from VIT, this research aims to enhance traditional testing methods, making them more efficient and accurate. The methodology involved scanning 100 carefully selected aggregates with a high-precision LiDAR scanner, reducing testing time by over 50%. The results showed a strong correlation between LiDAR and traditional manual testing, with an error margin of less than 2%. The study generated 3D models of aggregates, providing precise measurements of their dimensions.

The research highlighted several benefits of LiDAR, including increased efficiency, accuracy, and simplified data collection, with minimal human error. However, it also pointed out challenges such as alignment difficulties during scanning and the high cost of equipment. Future work includes expanding the sample size, developing automated alignment tools, and integrating AI for automated analysis. The research emphasizes the ethical considerations of data integrity and environmental impact and recommends the widespread adoption of LiDAR in the construction industry. The study concludes that LiDAR technology has the potential to revolutionize aggregate testing, offering a faster, more precise, and sustainable alternative to manual methods.